

POLITICA

Navigating the Paradox of Democracy and Military Control: An Analysis of an Imaginary Country's Political Landscape

To Cite:

Zaman, K. Navigating the Paradox of Democracy and Military Control: An Analysis of an Imaginary Country's Political Landscape. *Politica* 2023; Vol. 1, Issue 1, pp. 26-32.

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Peer-Review History

Received: 11 January 2023

Reviewed & Revised: 13/ January/2023 to 14/February/2023

Accepted: 16 February 2023

Published: March 2023

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

Politica

ISSN xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/journal-politica?authuser=0>

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

Khalid Zaman¹

ABSTRACT

The rise of a military-led "deep state" is a global phenomenon that seriously threatens democratic governments everywhere. A hypothetical nation called "Sherwan" has a military-led "deep state" that controls the government, the economy, and the media. The military maintains its grip on power through a convoluted system of manipulation and compulsion, all while hiding its true nature behind the facade of democratic institutions. A combination of the military's dominance of political parties and the election process and the government's efforts to silence the media and civil society have made it difficult for the country's citizens to have confidence in the democratic system. There is no possibility of enforcing responsibility or monitoring, allowing the military-led deep state to function without restraint. The military's obsession with its preservation slows economic growth by diverting resources from defence and undercutting free-market ideals. This research delves into the numerous facets of the military-led deep state. It considers potential responses to the threats it presents to democratic governance, open government, and the rule of law. This research, which uses the made-up nation of Sherwan as an example, sheds light on the workings of a military-led deep state and offers suggestions for combating it to promote freer, more democratic societies.

Keywords: Military-led deep state; Fantasy country; Conspiracy theories; Power game; Challenges; Solutions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The fact that "Deep State" occurs in the primary title of so many academic publications (4610 total) implies that it is a subject of interest and concern to many scholars in various fields. There has been a rise in the use of the phrase "Deep State" in recent years, notably in conversations about politics and government, both in the United States and elsewhere.

SHERWAN

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1.1. Arguments for and against the existence of a deep state

When people talk about the "deep state," they refer to a group of people who they think are working behind the scenes to influence government policy and political choices (Braun, 2019; Johnson, 2021). In recent years, this idea—often linked to conspiracy theories—has gained traction, notably in the United States (Douglas, 2019; Verma, 2020; Hellinger, 2018). The concept of a "deep state" is often founded on the premise that the government and other institutions are managed by an elite cabal immune to public and democratic review (Michaels, 2017). Supporters of the theory say that influential people act in their self-interest rather than the public good (Stroebe & Frey, 1982; Follesdal, 2010). On the other side, many who disagree with the deep state notion say it is nothing more than a conspiracy theory designed to undermine faith in government and democratic institutions (Dean, 2009; Baden & Sharon, 2021). They argue that there is no evidence to prove the existence of a hidden network of strong persons who can affect government policy and that the concept of a deep state is generally based on vague and unfounded allegations (Pozen, 2010; Molina et al. 2021). There are people and organizations with too much sway in many nations' governments and other authoritative bodies. Nevertheless, this does not prove there is no covert deep state at work (de Vries, 2006). They are more likely to be able to influence politics via legitimate channels like lobbying and campaign donations. There needs to be more evidence to establish a deep state as a cohesive and coordinated network, despite the fact that the idea may appeal to people distrustful of government and other organizations. When assessing political and social phenomena, one should be wary of statements that depend on indistinct or unproven assertions and instead look to complex data and facts.

1.2. Inconsistency of a military-controlled deep state with democratic values

The concept of a military-controlled deep state implies that the military is exerting influence over this shadowy organization and that its members are looking out for themselves rather than the public (Pedersen, 2011). It is worth noting that the idea of a "deep state," especially one dominated by the military, is fraught with controversy and supported by little hard evidence (O'Donnell, 2020; . Mainstream scholarship and journalism do not support the idea that the military or any other group is secretly controlling the government from behind the scenes, even though there may be instances of individuals acting in their self-interest or engaging in corrupt activities within government institutions. Furthermore, any military engagement in political matters should be subject to democratic monitoring and responsibility since armies exist to serve and defend their nations and inhabitants. While the military plays a vital role in ensuring national security, the concept of a military-controlled deep state that operates outside of democratic governance and accountability is antithetical to the ideals of a well-functioning democratic society (O'Connor, 2011).

1.3. Introduction to conspiracy theories related to a hypothetical military-led deep state

In place of hard proof, conspiracy theorists generally rely on conjecture and assumptions about who or what is behind an event or circumstance (Raikka, 2009). Every field, from politics and administration to science and medicine, is fair game for conspiracy theorists (Jolley & Douglas, 2014). Theories that vaccinations are part of a worldwide effort to control or damage people or that the moon landing was staged are both examples of conspiracy theories. Although some conspiracy theories may be founded on actual events or include kernels of truth, they frequently depend on little evidence (Cosentino, 2020). They may be destructive if they propagate misinformation or incite violence. When considering such beliefs, thinking critically and being dependent on trustworthy sources is necessary. However, the idea of a military-led deep state has inspired several conspiracy theories. First is the belief that the military manipulates and ultimately influences a country's political leadership via covert operations and other means. The military may resort to violence, extortion, or other means to influence politicians and further its goals. Second, the military and intelligence institutions are being run by hidden organizations, and there might be many different interests at play among these groups. Third, the military or the deep state stages false flag operations to further its agenda when someone other than the actual perpetrator of an assault or other event is blamed for it. Finally, dissent and criticism of the military's control are supposedly stifled by the "deep state. Censorship, propaganda, or even physical force may be used against their opponents.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE IMAGINARY COUNTRY

Let us make up a crafted nation named "Sherwan" for this exercise. The military in Sherwan has amassed so much power that they effectively run the nation and its civilian institutions. A sham of democracy, political parties are just vehicles for advancing special interests and silencing dissenters. The military in Sherwan controls the country's most important industries and resources, notably its oil, gas, and mineral reserves. They are also in charge of the country's infrastructure, including the roads, the phone lines, and the banks. This gives the military the power to control economic policy and direct the country's progress towards military goals. Regarding news and dissenting opinions, the military in Sherwan likewise has a firm hold over the media. They utilise their authority to stifle citizens' rights to free expression and assembly to keep a tight rein on the populace. Despite the country's autocratic government, the military in Sherwan employs political parties to provide the appearance of democracy. There are elections, but the military manipulates the results to guarantee that only their chosen candidates are elected. Existing political parties are generally either under the direct authority of the military or substantially influenced by them. The military in Sherwan also has a say in the country's diplomatic and military decisions abroad. These nations do such actions for their own benefit, whether it is natural resource control, geopolitical standing, or regional sway. Concerns about the erosion of democracy and the rule of law by a military-led deep state are warranted. A lack of democratic supervision and accountability means military decisions are made in secret and without input from the general populace. Corruption, power abuse, and human rights abuses are all possible outcomes. To solve this problem, it is essential to have a free press, a robust civil society, and an impartial court that can hold the military to account for its acts. Putting the military under the command of civilians elected to that position is also crucial, fostering a culture of democratic ideals such as openness, accountability, and regard for human rights. Only by advocating for these ideals can a democratic society flourish and the

military-led deep state be broken down.

3. INVESTIGATIVE FOCUS AND AIMS IN AN IMAGINARY COUNTRY

The following research questions are offered about the Sherwan economy.

- I. How does a military-led deep state differ from other kinds of authoritarianism, and what are its distinguishing characteristics?
- II. How does a deep state driven by the military function in reality, and what mechanisms does it utilize to keep power?
- III. How does a military-led deep state affect the country's long-term economic, social, and political growth?
- IV. How difficult is it to hold a deep state commanded by the military to account, and what safeguards can be implemented to maintain openness and oversight?
- V. What role do non-state entities like civil society, the media, and the like play in undermining the military-led deep state and bolstering democratic rule?
- VI. What are the options for dealing with a deep state dominated by the military, and what can we learn from the history of countries that have successfully opposed such regimes?
- VII. How can the rest of the world help in the fight against military-led "deep states" and for a democratic rule? And
- VIII. What ways are there to ensure regional and international safety in the face of the threats posed by a deep state dominated by the military?

In keeping with the research question, the following are the objectives of the investigation:

- I. To examine the features and functioning of a military-led deep state in a hypothetical economy.
- II. To investigate how a military-led deep state stays in power and how it impacts the country's economy, society, and government.
- III. To focus on increasing openness and watchdog activity inside a military-led "deep state" and
- IV. To evaluate the impact of non-state actors like civil society and the media on efforts to reform the military-led "deep state" and foster democratic rule.

4. VALUE OF THE STUDY

The study points out a few possible contributions, such as shedding insight into the strategies used by military-led deep governments to preserve their control and quash opposition in an alternative reality. The study's identification of these processes and analysis of their effect should aid in raising awareness of the dangers presented by military-led deep states and informing attempts to avoid their establishment or oppose their influence. The research also highlighted threats to democratic governance's openness, accountability, and the rule of law by investigating the effects of military-led deep states on these concepts. Due to this, the relevance of these ideals and the necessity to defend them against military-led deep states would be brought to a broader audience. Promoting openness and accountability, building democratic institutions, and boosting civil society involvement are ways the research helped inform efforts to fight the effect of military-led deep states. The study's recommendations provide helpful direction for either avoiding the rise of military-led deep states or opposing their influence in nations where it already exists. The research helps fill in the picture of the financial toll exacted by deep states run by the military. The research contributes to economic strategies that put growth and development ahead of the interests of a tiny elite by shedding light on how these regimes priorities their interests above broader economic progress. Ultimately, the research significantly adds to our knowledge of military-led deep regimes and the difficulties they provide to attempts at establishing representative government and advancing the economy. The research has the potential to encourage more open, transparent, and democratic societies by bringing attention to these dangers and suggesting potential remedies.

5. POLITICAL SYSTEM UNDER MILITARY-LED DEEP STATE

5.1. Control of political parties by the military

The military does not only run the government and the economy; they also back one political party or leader because they are in sync with their goals. In Sherwan, the military's preferred political party is typically given advantages over its rivals through funding and attention from the local media. Because of this, they have a distinct edge in elections, which are often influenced in their favour. The military-led deep state in Sherwan utilizes its influence to intimidate and compel opposition parties. This includes violence and threats against opposition leaders and their followers. This further diminishes the credibility of the electoral process and the ability of opposition parties to compete effectively in elections. A military-led deep state could take over the electoral process, naming their favourite candidate the winner, notwithstanding the election's results. It may spark demonstrations and civil disturbances, but the military usually steps in to end it. The military-led deep state in Sherwan could resort to various measures to preserve its holds on power, such as widespread monitoring of the populace or eliminating civil society groups that threaten their rule. These actions harm democracy, restrict fundamental freedoms of expression and assembly, and violate basic human rights. Furthermore, they allow those in charge to avoid responsibility for their actions and foster an atmosphere conducive to corruption and abuse of power. A transparent and impartial electoral body that can guarantee fair elections is needed to fix this problem. Supporting opposition parties and leaders who are working to promote democracy and human rights is also essential, as is international pressure and support from other countries in order to hold the military-led deep state accountable for its actions. A long-term dedication to advancing democratic principles and institutions and a willingness to stand up to authoritarianism and corruption would be required to bring down Sherwan's military-led deep state.

5.2. Elections being used as a façade

In our hypothetical circumstance, it may be exceedingly challenging to secure fair elections if the military-led deep state has already set the head of the electoral commission and included them in their operations. There are, however, specific measures that may be taken to lessen the impact of the problem. One option is to form a group of credible civil society groups, objective media outlets, and foreign observers to act as a watchdog and observer group. This group may keep an eye on the polls from beginning to finish, reporting any problems they find along the way. In addition, the group may check that the election commission is adhering to universal norms for fair voting. Providing a safe and confidential method for reporting election malpractices would be another crucial step. Because of this, more people may feel safe coming forward to report wrongdoings they have observed. Promoting public knowledge and education on democratic norms and procedures may also decrease the risk of election malpractices. Promoting free and fair elections, voter education, and the perils of electoral malpractices might require enlisting the help of civil society groups, the media, and other stakeholders. Foreign pressure and assistance may be essential in supporting free and fair elections in such a setting. International organizations, governments, and civil society groups can promote transparent and credible elections by advocating for them and providing resources and assistance to local civil society organizations, the media, and election observers. While it may be difficult to guarantee free and fair elections when the commission's leader is unmovable, some measures may be taken to improve the situation and make the electoral process more democratic. In order to implement these measures, there must be concerted efforts to promote democratic principles and institutions, as well as robust collaborations between civil society, the media, and international organizations.

5.3. Role of election commission under the military-led deep state

In a hypothetical country like Sherwan, where a military-led deep state is in charge, ensuring free and fair elections may be difficult. However, creating an open and impartial electoral body may help advance the cause of legitimate elections. For starters, the electoral commission has to be formed with members who can make decisions without being swayed by the military-led deep state. One way to do this is to use an open and inclusive process to choose members, including a broad spectrum of civil society groups and other relevant parties. Voter registration, polling, vote counting, and the declaration of results are all components of the election process that must fall within the purview of the electoral commission. They must be allowed to investigate allegations of vote rigging or voter intimidation and rule on them. The electoral commission has to be given the authority to operate transparently and responsibly to guarantee fair elections. They must disseminate all information about the election, including but not limited to the rules, processes, and results. In addition, they need to let impartial observers watch the election and report on it to assure its legitimacy and independence. Election commissions may employ tools like electronic voting machines, online voter registration, and digital counting and tabulation systems to increase public confidence in the integrity of the electoral process. This can make voting more secure, quicker, and less susceptible to human mistakes or fraud. It is crucial to increase public trust in the electoral commission and the election process in a context where the military-led deep state controls many areas of the electoral process. Education and awareness initiatives may help by informing voters of their rights and obligations as voters and the electoral commission's role in holding fair and transparent elections (Arthur, 2010). Promoting credible and fair elections relies heavily on establishing a transparent and independent electoral commission (Chipenzi, 2016). However difficult it may be in a made-up country like Sherwan, it is nevertheless a necessary action in fostering democratic principles and establishing a robust and healthy democratic society.

5.4. Role of judiciary under the military-led deep state

Even if a military-led deep state exists and dominates most elements of society, the court may still play an essential role in maintaining the rule of law and advancing democratic norms. The judiciary plays a crucial role in society by serving as a neutral and objective place where legal issues may be settled, and laws are enforced. When the military-led deep state is in charge, the court may consider cases involving election malpractices, human rights violations, and other concerns. Judiciary may serve as a check on the authority of the military-led deep state by ensuring it operates within the bounds of the law and the constitution. This may include holding trials on the legality of activities performed by the military-led deep state and rendering an impartial verdict on whether or not these actions violate the law or democratic standards. Judicial appointments should be made based on merit and independence rather than political factors to ensure that the judiciary can fulfill its constitutional mandate. Judges must be allowed to make judgments according to the law and the facts without fear of retribution or influence from the military-led deep state. The judiciary may advance public trust and confidence by keeping all court procedures accessible to the press and public and making rulings by well-established legal precedent. The public's faith in the judicial system can be bolstered, and the military-led deep state's acts can be held to account if this is implemented. Foreign support and pressure are also crucial in bolstering an independent judiciary in such a circumstance. International organizations, governments, and civil society groups may support the court by providing resources, technical help, training, and advocacy for a fair and impartial judiciary (Squatrito, 2021). However difficult it may be for the court to do its job while a military-led deep state is in power, it is essential to maintaining democracy and the rule of law.

6. MILITARY DOMINANCE AND CONTROL IN SHERWAN

When the military is in charge of a country's "deep state," it is typically also in charge of the government and other institutions, including the courts. Because the military may be able to influence or dominate the legal system, it may be challenging to hold the military-led deep state responsible via conventional legal methods. However, the military can have internal methods for holding personnel responsible for wrongdoing or breaches of military law. Military personnel who break the law or conduct irresponsibly may face court-martial or internal disciplinary punishment. Although the military may be hesitant to hold itself responsible, it is vital to remember that the military is frequently the primary source of power and control under a deep state run by the military. In this kind of

setting, it is essential to have a free and independent press, a strong civil society, and an impartial court to provide responsibility for wrongdoing outside the scope of the military. It is necessary to establish a larger framework for accountability that is outside of the military and represents democratic norms and principles, even while the military may have its internal systems for holding its members responsible.

6.1. Challenges of implementing laissez-faire economics in a military-led deep state

Laissez-faire economics, sometimes known as free-market economics, is a school of thought that promotes limited government involvement in business and industry (Henry, 2008). The government's function in a laissez-faire economy is confined to safeguarding private property, enforcing contracts, and ensuring the rule of law (Chandra, 2021). According to this idea, the market can and should function with little oversight from the state. Executing a laissez-faire economy in a hypothetical military-led deep state may be challenging when the military controls the government and institutions. The military-led deep state's priority may be self-preservation above support for free enterprise. Without the safeguards of the rule of law and independent institutions, property rights and contracts may be more vulnerable, making it more difficult to sustain a laissez-faire economic model. In addition, a military-led deep state may care more about preserving its authority than defending the nation from external threats. Because of this, military spending may be cut, leaving the nation exposed to attack. A hypothetical military-led deep state may not be the best fit for a free-market economy since the military would likely prioritize its survival above advancing free trade. To avoid corruption in any field, economic or otherwise, it is crucial to have a government that answers to the people and institutions that can act as checks and balances.

7. THE MEDIA'S ROLE IN PROTECTING THE SHERWAN ECONOMY

The media has an essential regulator role by reporting on abuses of power and breaches of human rights by the government and other vital interests (Suzor, 2019). The media may serve as a check on the authority of the military-led deep state if it reports on their acts and exposes any abuses of power or corruption they may be engaging in. Increased public understanding and mobilization of public opinion against the military-led deep state may result from this. By objectively reporting on political events and conducting investigations into and reporting on problems linked to government policies and acts, the media may play a significant role in fostering an environment of openness and accountability. This may give way for the public to monitor government choices and hold the military-led deep state responsible for their activities. By reporting on elections fairly and objectively, encouraging citizens to become informed voters, and hosting open forums for public discourse, the media may help spread support for democratic principles and practices. This may give a means for people to have a voice in government and help restore faith in democratic institutions. To fulfill this function effectively, the media must be protected from governmental censorship and coercion, function freely without fear of punishment, and report the news without fear of reprisal. In addition, the media has an obligation to its audience to offer accurate and fair coverage of all issues. The international community's backing and pressure may be necessary to help independent media survive under these conditions. As well as advocating for press freedom and independent media, international organizations, governments, and civil society groups may contribute resources, technical aid, and training to support the media. The media is a crucial institution in promoting democratic ideas and preventing a nation from being entirely dominated by the military, even though it may find it difficult to operate efficiently in a scenario when a military-led deep state is in power.

8. CONSTITUTIONAL PROTECTIONS FOR THE SHERWAN ECONOMY

Changes to the Constitution may be essential if a nation is threatened by a military-led deep state and wants to prevent the military from seizing power. The condition of affairs and the make-up of the military-led deep state will determine what kinds of reforms, if any, are necessary. Potential amendments to the Constitution might include the following; first, constitutional amendments that establish a clear line of authority should keep the military and civilian administration strictly distinct. This may include establishing a free and independent press capable of holding the military to account, as well as a strong and independent legislature. Second, the Constitution might be changed to prevent military members from running for office or joining political parties. Third, electoral commissions, political parties, and civil society groups are all examples of democratic institutions that constitutional amendments might bolster. Fourth, the Constitution might be modified to include such provisions to guarantee that the military promotes human rights and protects civilians, and fifth, the military's operations could be monitored, and the military would be held responsible for any abuses of power if independent monitoring mechanisms were established by constitutional amendment. In the grand scheme of things, amending the Constitution may be a significant step towards averting or dealing with a deep state driven by the military. It is essential, however, that any modifications be made democratically and inclusively and accurately represent the people's will.

9. STUDY REFLECTIONS

The military-led deep state in the crafted nation of Sherwan poses severe problems for democratic rule. It is difficult to question the military's supremacy because of its broad and far-reaching influence over significant institutions, such as politics, the media, and the economy. Threatening the credibility of the democratic system is the repression of free media and civil society and election process manipulation. There is no possibility of enforcing responsibility or monitoring, allowing the military-led deep state to function without restraint. Even with these obstacles, there may be methods to fight against the military-led deep state. It is possible to restore faith in democratic institutions by creating a fully independent court and guaranteeing the impartiality and openness of election commissions. The military-led deep state may be challenged if civil society and free media are bolstered. Constitutional reforms are necessary to avoid the military becoming an all-consuming force in the country's progress, including steps to restrict the military's engagement in politics and its influence over the economy. At its core, the threat posed by the military-led deep state is not one of political power or

economic supremacy but of democracy and human rights. We can only expect to create more open, transparent, and democratic societies that are responsive to the demands of their residents if we acknowledge this difficulty and strive towards answers.

10. ACTIONABLE STEPS

Given their dominance over society, holding a military-led deep state responsible may be complicated and challenging. Nonetheless, several tools are available for enforcing their accountability and spreading democratic principles. For starters, civilian institutions like the court, civil society groups, and independent media may all play essential roles in keeping the military-led deep state responsible. Abuse of authority may be uncovered, corruption and human rights breaches reported on, and political reforms promoted with the help of these organizations. These organizations may constrain the military-led deep state and advance democratic principles by increasing public knowledge and rallying public opinion. Second, foreign organizations and institutions may play a significant role in enforcing accountability on the part of the military-led deep state. International institutions like the United Nations and the International Criminal Court may investigate and prosecute human rights abuses and breaches of international law. The military-led deep state may be pressured to reform its conduct and follow democratic standards via international sanctions. Third, the military-led deep state may be held responsible via diplomatic pressure and engagement. Countries may use diplomatic and economic penalties against a country that refuses to recognize a military-run government if they want to modify its conduct. It can encourage political transformation and human rights protection via diplomatic channels. Overall, it takes a concerted effort on a national and international scale to bring a military-led deep state to justice. It is feasible to restrict the authority of the military-led deep state and create a more democratic and accountable government by constructing robust and independent institutions, promoting democratic principles, and utilizing diplomatic and legal measures to exert pressure on the deep state.

11. IMPEDIMENTS TO THE STUDY

The fact that the research assumes the existence of a nation named "Sherwan" is a significant caveat. While this may help study military-led deep states in a lab setting, it may not accurately represent the complexity and subtleties of real-world examples. The research needs more empirical evidence to adequately evaluate the consequences of military-led deep states since it is based on a hypothetical example. It may not be easy to properly convey these regimes' complex and dynamic character, even while the analysis may depend on previous research and case studies of real-world situations. Given the complexity and breadth of difficulties that may entail military-led deep states, the research may not be able to investigate all of their facets and concerns in detail.

12. ANTICIPATED DEVELOPMENTS AND OPPORTUNITIES

In order to better understand the causes and effects of these regimes, future studies should concentrate on particular real-world instances of deep states, relying on empirical data and interviews with important players. The elements contributing to the genesis and maintenance of deep states may be more easily identified via a comparative investigation of several examples. Efforts to build democratic institutions, promote openness and accountability, and involve civil society are all potential responses to deep states that might be the subject of future study. The consequences of military-led deep states on economic growth, especially resource allocation, investment, and expansion, might benefit from further study. The study provides an exquisite starting point with the help of a hypothetical country case for further analysis of the complicated and problematic subject of military-led deep states. There is a great lot of promise for future research in this area.

Author's Disclaimer

The authors of this work emphasize that the research given here is hypothetical and in no way represents the authors' actual worldview or set of values. There is no malice or discriminatory intent behind this research; rather, it is meant as a lighthearted exercise to consider some exciting possibilities. The objective of this research is purely academic; no person or political organization is meant to be singled out in any way. The views expressed in this work are those of the authors alone and do not reflect those of any group, institution, or government body.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance..

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

Not Applicable.

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